

Maximization of Ln of Arrangements versus the Canonical/Grand Canonical Approaches

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 25, 2023

Maximizing \ln of the number of arrangements (using factorials) subject to the constraint $\sum_i n_i e_i$ to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is a common procedure in statistical mechanics. A similar procedure is given in (1) for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein (BE) approaches, but in this case the degeneracy g_i of a single energy level e_i is introduced and is crucial to solving the problem. In fact, one calculates the way to distribute n_i (average number of) particles in level i among the g_i degenerate cells for the BE case. Maximizing with respect to the constraints $\sum_i n_i e_i = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i n_i = N_{ave}$ yields the BE distribution which is multiplied by g_i . Alternatively, one may use the grand canonical approach which uses weights of $\exp(-(E-uN)/T)$ where T is temperature and u the chemical potential.

The issue we raise is that the factorial arrangement approach depends critically on a single particle degeneracy g_i , while the grand canonical does not, yet both yield the same result, the BE distribution. (Note: One may take the BE distribution function obtained from the grand canonical approach and multiply it by g_i at the end of the calculation.). Thus we suggest that one should be able to establish a factorial/arrangement approach which does not depend on the degeneracy g_i of a single cell. The objective of this note is to show the link between a factorial/permutation approach which does not use e_i degeneracy with the grand canonical approach.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and the Canonical Approach

Consider distributing a total energy E over N particles. It is assumed that all distributions have the same probability. Thus one imagines an equilibrium scenario with n_i values (with the strict E constraint eased to $\sum_i n_i e_i = E$) and calculates the number of permutations:

$$N! / \prod_i n_i! \quad ((1a)) \text{ and maximizes subject to } \sum_i n_i e_i = E \quad ((1b))$$

to obtain the MB distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

This approach seems, however, to follow more directly from information theory. Consider tossing a coin four times. One may obtain 4 heads, 4 tails, 3 heads 1 tail (various permutations) and 2 tails 2 heads (various permutations). As the number of tosses N , however, approaches infinite the number of heads should equal the number of tails and so different trial runs simply produce different permutations, each with the same probability. Thus this probability is in fact:

$$1 / \{\text{number of permutations } ((1a))\} \quad ((2))$$

n_i is considered an average over systems with different energies i.e. this approach is equivalent to the $\exp(-E/T)$ canonical one. One may note that no single particle degeneracy

arguments appear. The main idea is that a factorial scheme emerges because all probability runs are permutations of each other when N approaches infinite.

Thus one may maximize ((1a)) subject to ((1b)) or consider:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{information} = \text{constant } e_i \quad ((3))$$

Thus, information is equivalent to energy with constant = $-1/T$, T =temperature.

We try to extend this idea to the grand canonical approach.

Grand Canonical Approach

In the grand canonical case, one eases the exact constraints E and N , but the goal is still to find: $n(e_i)$. The two constraints are now:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i) = N_{\text{ave}} \quad ((4b))$$

As a result, instead of having a trial run of N probability results, one should have a trial run of N_1 results, N_2 results etc. It seems, however, that N_1 , N_2 , N_3 etc all tend to infinite. Thus given an average $n(e_i)$, some particles are associated with N_1 , others with N_2 etc. In the limit of all N tending to infinite these various distributions of the $n(e_i)$ particles should all carry the same weight. In such a case, one needs to calculate the number of arrangements. We note that no mention of degeneracy within a single particle e_i level (i.e. momentum directions) is required. Instead we introduce a parameter b which describes the number of N_i 's being considered. Then the number of arrangements within a given e_i is:

$$\frac{(n(e_i) + b - 1)!}{\{n(e_i)! (b-1)!\}} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) may be maximized with respect to ((4a)), ((4b)) to obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution. "b" appears as a factor in front and does not affect the form of the BE distribution.

Next, we wish to link the factorial approach ((5)) directly with the grand canonical approach. As in the MB case, we consider information as represented by the constraint ((4a)), ((4b)) i.e.

$$\text{Information} = -(e_i - u)/T \quad ((6))$$

The probability, however, is no longer $p(e_i)$ because one may 0,1,2,3,4.... particles in a level in the grand canonical approach. Thus probability for a single e_i is:

$$\left\{ \text{Sum over } n \text{ } p(e_i)^n \right\} \quad ((7))$$

We take the \ln to convert a product of ((7)): Product over e_i to a sum. Then:

$$\ln\left\{ \text{Sum over } n \text{ } p(e_i)^n \right\} = \ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - p(e_i)} \right) = \ln(Z_n) \quad ((8))$$

Here $\ln(Z_n)$ represents the portion linked with n .

The question is what is $p(e_i)$? This probability has nothing to do with the sum over n values i.e. it should be the same probability as in the MB case i.e. a distribution of E over N particles. Thus, using the constraints in this case, we suggest:

$$p(e_i) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T) \quad ((9))$$

Thus among the different E 's, one still distributes according to the canonical approach discussed in the first paragraph. The sum over n occurs for each single energy level e_i , showing that the additional physics is at this level. This is important because it is relevant to scattering. One no longer writes $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ for elastic scattering $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ even though $p(e_i)$ still has the MB form.

With ((9)), one may see from ((7)) that: $z \frac{d}{dz} \ln(Z_n) = \langle n \rangle$ where $z = \exp(u/T)$ i.e.

$$n(e_i) \text{ average} = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T) / \{ 1 - \exp(-(e_i - u)/T) \} \quad ((10)) \text{ Bose-Einstein distribution}$$

The approach of allowing different numbers of n in a single particle state is equivalent to allowing different total N_1, N_2, N_3 values, we argue. Thus the factorial approach and ((8)), ((9)) should yield the same result.

Single Particle Degeneracy

A point we wish to suggest is that even though single energy level e_i degeneracy exists (e.g. different momentum vector directions may have the same magnitude) and is important when summing over e_i (i.e. converting a sum to an integral over momentum), it does not enter into the calculation of the form of the MB or BE distributions. Thus when maximizing arrangements, one does not necessarily consider all degrees of freedom in a problem. This suggests that entropy is not really the maximization of all degrees of freedom. The factorial expression appears because it is equivalent to the probability of N trial probability runs when N approaches infinite. In the case of $N_1, N_2, N_3 \dots$ all tending to infinite, $n(e_i)$ average is considered to be partitioned among different N_1, N_2, N_3 scenarios, but with each partitioning yielding the same probability in the infinite N_i limit. Thus the number of arrangements is again linked to a probability value and it is p probability (not disorder or maximization of all degrees of freedom) which is minimized, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the canonical and grand canonical approaches, one minimizes the probability of a large N run of trials with N approaching infinite. In this case, each trial run yields the same actual events except with different permutations, we argue. For example, tossing a coin a few times does not yield the same values simply permuted, but if one tosses it

an infinite number of times, one expects equal numbers of heads or tails. Small variations against infinitely large numbers are insignificant. Thus one may calculate an arrangement expression using permutations/factorials to represent the probability and minimize it with respect to appropriate constraints. We note that one does not maximize all possible arrangements in the system. For example, there may be energy degeneracies due to momentum pointing in different directions, but this does not affect the overall form of the MB or BE distribution forms, although it appears when adding over e_i (i.e. converting to an integral over momentum) i.e. it affects the density of states.

As a result, in the MB or canonical case, one considers \ln of permutations: $\ln \{N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)\}$ subject to $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{ave}$. For the grand canonical case, we argue that single energy level degeneracies need not be considered as they are in (1). We suggest that in terms of e_i , there is a $p(e_i)$ which still follows the MB distribution approach, but now associated with the constraints: $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i n(e_i) = N_{ave}$ i.e. $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$. Here $-1/T$ is the Lagrange multiplier associated with the E_{ave} constraint and u/T with the N_{ave} one.

The grand canonical approach, however, considers different $N_1, N_2, N_3 \dots$ values, each of which tend to infinite. Thus we argue that in this limit there should again be a permutation expression associated with the particles of $n(e_i)$ average which are associated with N_1, N_2 etc. We suggest b N_i values and write: $\ln \{ (n(e_i) + b - 1)! / [n(e_i)! (b - 1)!] \}$ and maximize, subject to the two constraints. This is equivalent to different n numbers in each $p(e_i)$ state. Thus we consider: $\ln(Z_n) = \ln \{ \sum_n p(e_i)^n \}$ for a specific e_i . The N portion of the grand canonical approach is linked with each e_i level. The sum is a geometric one and as shown one obtains the BE distribution. Thus we argue that the factorial permutation expression and the grand canonical approach are one and the same and that single particle degeneracy plays no part in obtaining the e_i form of the MB or BE distributions.

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) page 182